

Shea Nuts Drying Machine: A Tool for enhancing Productivity and Shelf life of Shea fruit and the Derivatives

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Abstract

Shea butter is a very valuable product extracted from shea nuts and utilized in varied applications in food processing, cosmetics and pharmaceutical fields. The procedure involves in its post-processing from shea nuts ranges drying (or roasting), milling, boiling, extraction to packaging. Shea related products become less appreciated when they contain excess moisture content. Excessive moisture in shea fruit encourages rancidity of the oil and necessitates presence of more moisture in its oil. The traditional methods of achieving moisture reduction process, basically by drying or roasting is often done either by sun-drying or roasting the nuts on metal pans fired with heaps of firewood, requires length of days to achieve. These age-long techniques do not only expose the operators to danger but also promote rancidity of the oil due to increase in the enzyme activities, reduction in the product quality and dwindling in the productivity in the midst of ever-increasing demand. The application of improved methods using suitable machines and equipment would alleviate these challenges. This research focused on the development and assessment of the performance of a 10 kg per batch shea nuts drying machine. Its comprises, basically, the chutes (inlet and discharge) unit, drying chamber fired with 5.0 kW heating element 1.0 gear reduction motor, 4.0 kW dimmer control switch and frame structure. The developed machine was evaluated to dry 10.0 kg, with initial moisture content of 28.44 % for four hours, and the procedure replicated five times. The results obtained showed that has agro-allied product reduces in mass as its moisture loss increases. It was concluded that the use of this device would alleviate the yearning of the stakeholders, boost the production capacity of shea related products and prolong the shelf life of shea fruits

Keywords—Shea butter, applications, traditional methods, challenges, shea nuts drying machine, Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Shea butter is an edible oil or fat with potential for medicinal applications. It is used: as additive to sauces, skin pomade, and ingredient for soap making; ointment for curing headache, leprosy (ailment) and aiding childbirth delivery, and a cocoa butter equivalent in the manufacture of chocolate. Besides, it is used as biofuel for traditional lanterns and vegetable oils for frying meals. More so, shea cake, the left-over which is a mixture of the chaff enriches with fraction of unrecovered oil and moisture, is used as fuel and additive in livestock feed production (Opeke, 1992 1994; Eka, 1997; Olaniyan and Oje, 1999 2002; Alonge and Olaniyan, 2000; 2002; Alander, 2004). Shea nut is characterized with an oil content ranging from 45 to 60 % (Opeke, 1992; Garba et al., 2011)

Shea butter is extracted from shea fruit. Shea fruit consists of a green epicarp (the outer part), a fleshy mesocarp (pulp), and a relatively hard and brown

endocarp (shell); The endocarp(shell) when cracked releases the embryo (Shea kernel), which after drying to prevent degradation, is processed into Shea butter. The tree was named by the German (Botanist Carl Gaertner as *Vitellaria paradoxa*. Shea tree is a medium-sized tree of the *Sapotecae* (soapberry) family and genus *Vitellaria*; It has a botanical name *Butryospermum parkli*, with other names such as: *Karite* (French), *Nku* (Ghana) and *Ese* or *Ori* (Yoruba). It is believed to have been a native to sub-Saharan Africa, and generally found in semi-arid to arid areas north of the humid forest zone (CABI, 2003; Chalfin, 2004; Olaniyan and Oje (2007); Nwannewuihe *et al.*, 2016). Notable among countries where this crop is grown in Africa include: Ghana, Burkina Faso and Nigeria. Nigeria has been found to be the main exporters of Shea nut, according to Hee (2011). In Nigeria, the Shea tree grows in Niger, Kwara, Kebbi, Kaduna and Oyo states. Nigeria's Shea nut production also ranks high globally as it produces about 50 % of the

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world's Shea nut, but tends to consume most of it locally (Karen, 2005).

The post-processing of shea nuts/fruits into variant products involves series of stages, ranging from picking during harvest to sorting, drying, winnowing, sterilization, digestion, clarification and packaging. These processing stages often vary from region to region(s) and among stakeholders engaging in it depending on the output desired to be achieved. The different methods, commencing from gathering, processing and initiating treating the shea nuts, are presumed to be a major underlying cause in the difference in the quality characteristics among the shea butter extracted from different places. One of the most important characteristics of biological materials is their moisture content. The moisture content of agro-allied and bio-materials affects their physical, chemical and mechanical properties. Shea kernel with high moisture content are not suitable for butter extraction (Hall *et al.*, 1996); they yield butter that is less appreciated due to the hydrolytic and oxidative degradations, which enhances the acidity and rancidity of the oil (Honfo *et al.*, 2020). Shea nuts generally undergo high enzyme activities; the after-effects include production of shea butter characterized by high level of iodine number, high percentage of free fatty acid, peroxide value, microbes, inconsistent quality/yield and other solid and dissolved impurities. (Lovett, 2004; Kashaninejad *et al.*, 2005; Esiegbuya *et al.*, 2014). Thus, the shelf life of shea nut can be enhanced by reducing its moisture content.

Several researchers have studied and reported on the relationship between moisture content of bio-materials (shea fruits) and their properties. Olaniyan and Oje (2002) investigated the effect of compressive strength on heat-treated shea nuts in order to evaluate impacts of temperature and loading position rupture force, deformation, roughness and firmness of the nuts. From the study, they observed that rupture force, deformation and toughness decreased, whilst firmness increased with increase in temperature in both axial and lateral loading positions of the nuts and concluded that the manner of loading of shea nut has a strong influence on its strength properties under compressive loading conditions. Nwannewuihe *et al.*, (2016) studied the effect of physical properties on the specific heat of preserved ground shea kernel (*Butrospermum paradoxum*). They evaluated the specific heat of shea nut kernel at four levels of moisture contents (10 %, 20 %, 30 % and 40 %), and over five range

temperatures (50 °C, 60 °C, 70 °C, 80 °C and 90 °C) as a function of particle size (2.36 mm, 1.18 mm, 1.00 mm). They observed that the effect of moisture content is greater than both particle size and temperature. However, in spite of all attempts made to increase the quantity and enhance the quality of shea butter produced, the supply is still inadequate; this could be attributed to militating challenges ((its processing) at post-harvesting stage. According to Alonge and Olaniyan, (2007), the problem of shea butter starts at harvesting of its fruits. They opined that among the factors confronting the post-harvesting storage of shea nuts is as the lack of facilities for parboiling them immediately after harvesting. They also observed that more improved shea butter would have been produced if the method of processing (such as application of pre-extraction heat and roasting) and handling them had been improved on. More so, the drying or roasting of the shea nuts after harvest to reduce their water contents either for the purpose of preserving them for other planting season or processing them to valuable product(s), such as shea butter or shea oil from the shell which is an important process in the overall processing operations, has not been an easy task. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to develop and evaluate the performance of a 10 kg/h shea nuts drying machine, which would be capable of alleviating the challenge confronting stakeholders engaging in post-harvesting stage who could not afford the costs of imported ones tailored for the purpose.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Machine Design

The drying machine was designed with the aid of existing engineering standards and formulae, and drawn with SolidWorks software.

Selection of Shape and determination of size of the Drying chamber

Shea nuts have average density of 616.13 kg/m³ and average volume of 0.0182m³ (Aviara *et al.*, 2005). Thus, the volume of drying chamber required for processing the rated capacity of shea nuts at 40 % (β) loading factor was calculated with Equation (1):

$$V_{dc} = \frac{\pi}{4} [d_2^2 - d_1^2] (1 + 0.01\beta) \quad (1)$$

By convention, drying chambers of rotary drying systems are often cylindrical in shape; this is due to its innate ability to transfer heat and facilitate evenly spreading of the item (feedstock) being dried as it does not have edges where materials could get stuck in. However, for

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the purpose of having a better dimension/configuration so as to achieve optimum system performance, a computer program was written in python programming language to vary the length and diameter so as to obtain optimum geometric dimensions (length and diameter). Table 1 presents ranking of the dimensions for selecting optimum sizes for the drying chamber.

Table 1: Ranking of the dimensions of drying chamber for optimum system performance

S/N	Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	S/N
1	200	508.147	1
2	400	359.314	2
3	600	293.379	3
4	800	254.073	4
5	1000	227.25	5
6	1200	207.45	6
7	1400	192.061	7
8	1600	179.657	8
9	1800	169.382	9

From Table 1, it was observed that using cylinder with geometric properties S/N-1 or SN-2 would give rise to a chamber with widest diameter and shortest length which might not aid effective/even distribution of heat into the feedstock as they would be clogged. More so, choosing a dimension with length above 800 mm would make the internal wall of the chamber difficult to be accessed due to their reduced diameters and might cause the chamber to buckle when put to use. Hence, maintenance cost would be quite high. Therefore, cylinder with dimensions 600 mm (length) by 300 mm (diameter) was selected for this component.

The thickness of the drying chamber was determined with Equation 2;

$$t = \frac{Pd}{2\sigma} \quad (2)$$

The calculated thickness of material required for developing the drying chamber is 2.72 mm. Hence, 3 mm thick material was adopted.

Determination of Power rating of Heating system

The average weight of fresh nut is 9.7 g, while the average weight of dried nut is 6.0g (Boffa *et al.*, 2000). The moisture content of fresh shea fruits range from 67 % (Maranz *et al.*, 2004) to 80.3 % (Mbaiguinam *et al.*, 2007) Shea nuts are often dried to 4.76 – 10 % moisture content for safe storage to prevent spoilage (Esiogbuya *et al.*, 2014) and maintained at 10.24 % to achieve the best cracking rate (Gana *et al.*, 2016). The quantity of

water, in form of moisture, to be removed to achieve the desired moisture level was estimated with Equation (3)

$$m_w = \left(\frac{\phi_2 - \phi_1}{100 - M_1} \right) m_n \quad (3)$$

Hence, the size of heating element (P_h) required to achieve the heating process was determined, using the modified Equation (4)

$$P_h \text{ (kW)} = \frac{t}{50\eta} \{ m_w (c_w \Delta T + h_{fg}) + m_s c_s \Delta T \} \quad (4)$$

where m_w is the mass of water present in the nut to be dried off to attain the required moisture level; m_s is mass of solid part of the shea nut; c_w and c_s are specific heat capacities of water and shea nut (kJ/kg.K); h_{fg} is specific latent heat of vaporization of water (kJ/kg); ΔT is temperature difference ($^{\circ}\text{C}$); t is drying time (minute); η is thermal efficiency of the heating element; ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are the initial and final moisture contents of the shea nuts (%), and m_n is the mass of fresh shea nuts.

Estimation of Speed of rotation

By standard, rotating dryers are designed with a rotational speed (N) ranging from 5 – 25 rpm. The choice of considering moderate speed of rotation relies on the need to increase the residence time to facilitate even distribution of heat on, or absorption of heat by, the materials being dried; Based on this, an optimum speed of 20 rpm was chosen. Thus, for the purpose of preventing slipping and creeping when belt and pulley system is considered or cost to be incurred when gearing or gear reduction motor is used, Sprocket and Chain was selected. The rated speed of a single-phase electric motor is 1440 rpm; the speed ratio (N_r) was determined with Equation (5)

$$N_r = \frac{N_e}{N_d} \quad (5)$$

Hence, the calculated speed ratio is 7.2:1. Due to the sizes (diameters) of power transmission components (sprockets) that would be required to achieve the desired speed (N_d), which might increase the bending component of the moment, a compound chain-sprocket system was used. The speed ratio (N_r), with reference to the individual speed ratios (N_{r1} and N_{r2}) of each pair of sprockets is given by Equation (6):

$$N_r = N_{r1} \cdot N_{r2} \quad (6)$$

For the purpose of reducing noise due to vibration, and sagging or wobbling when sprocket characterized with small bore diameter is selected, the minimum number on each of the smaller sprockets utilized for achieving the speed ratios was restricted to 12 teeth but their bore diameters modified to accommodate the connecting pins

Determination of the properties (lengths) of chains

The length of each of the chains was determined with modified Equation (7), described by Sharma and Kamlesh (2013);

$$L_c = p \left[0.5Z_1(N_m + 1) + \frac{pZ_1^2(N_m - 1)^2}{4\pi^2 C} + \frac{2C}{p} \right] \quad (7)$$

and the number chain links (K) required to achieve the chain length (L_c) was estimated with Equation (8)

$$L_c = Kp$$

when values substituted, the K required are 109 and 118 pieces

Figure 1 presents the isometric drawing of the developed shea nuts drying machine produced with SolidWorks computer software (2014 Version)

Figure 1: 3D view of the developed Shea fruit drying machine

Performance Assessment of the developed shea nuts drying Machine

The performance characteristics of the developed shea nuts drying machine were assessed based on the final moisture attained over the drying period, drying rate, drying efficiency, percentage energy consumption and number of shea nuts cracked pieces recorded as a result of the reduction in the moisture contents. The assessment was based on the assumption that the drying process is continuous and that the falling rate take place steadily.

Drying Rate (D_r)

It denotes the characterization of the dehydration rate during the drying process. It is the time duration required to dry the shea fruit from its initial mass (m_1) to the required final mass (m_2). Using the Equation adopted by Ojediran *et al.* (2021), it was determined with equation (8)

$$D_r = - \frac{m_1 - m_2}{\Delta t} \quad (8)$$

Energy consumption

The energy consumption of the drying system refers to the efficiency of the drying process; it is the ratio of the energy utilized usefully to remove the moisture content from the charged feedstock (materials) to the total energy. it was calculated with the modified Equation (9), as described by Zhiheng *et al.*, (2024)

$$\eta_{ec} = \frac{D_r \cdot h_{fg}}{Q_h \Delta_t} \quad (9)$$

where: h_{fg} refers to latent of vaporization with a value of 2.26 kJ/kg; D_r is the feedstock drying rate (kg/h); Q_h is the power rating of the heating element (kW), and Δ_t is the drying time (hour)

Moisture shrink

moisture shrink, which is expressed as water or moisture shrink loss, is the amount of water lost as the produce (feedstock) dries to a standard moisture content. The moisture shrink (MC_s), was determined with Equation (10), according to Maier and Bakker-Arkem (2002)

$$MC_s = 100 \left(\frac{\theta_2 - \theta_1}{100 - M_1} \right) \quad (10)$$

Materials and equipment used for fabrication

Some of the materials used in the construction of this machine include: Sheet of mild steel (MS), lengths of 50 by 50 by 5 mm MS angle iron, fasteners such as: pieces of M3, M6, M10 and M12 Bolts and nuts, and MS electrode (Gauge 10) pairs of sprockets and chains .and 2 pieces of M206 Bearing were sourced within Akure Metropolis, the electric motor and heating element procured from Owode Market, Lagos State. The choice of selecting each of these materials was based on the results of the design analysis and available relevant engineering standards.

The equipment used include: Manual Metallic-Arc Welding machine; Drilling machine; Grinding machine; cutting and grinding discs; sets of spanners (flats and rings)

Plate 1 shows the photograph of the developed shea fruits drying machine

Plate 1 Photograph of the developed shea fruits drying machine

Control of the machine operation

For the purpose of ensuring wider range of rotational speed so as to cater for situations where a lesser mass of the feedstock or feedstock with improved moisture content(s) needed to be dried, a 3.0 kW dimmer control was incorporated into the machine. Also, to prevent the temperature from getting overboard and in turn burns off the charged feedstock, which could lead wastage of resources, a temperature regulator was installed. Figure 2 shows the electrical circuit diagram of the developed shea nuts dryer

Figure 2: Circuit diagram of the electrical control Panel During connection, a pair terminal (live and neutral) of the dimmer switch (a device for controlling the supplied voltage) was connected to one of the two pieces of 2.5 kW heating element used and the second pair of the its terminal connected with the power source terminal. More so, the probe of the thermocouple (50 – 100 °C) was mounted directly on the drum so as to enable it to be in direct contact with air circulating within the drum chamber; this was done to provide the ability to monitor and adjust the temperature over the range desired. Figure 2 shows the electrical circuit diagram of the developed shea nuts dryer

Parts description of the dryer

The developed drying machine consists of six functional units, namely: chutes (inlet and discharge), pair of electrical heating element, drying chamber, dimmer control mechanism, mechanical power transmission and mainframe. The h generating chamber uses two sets of electric heating elements, each of 2.5 kW. The drying chamber consists of hollow cylindrical drum, 1, 200 mm length of 50 mm hollow shaft, flight, faceplate cover and door, it was developed with 3 mm thick stainless steel. the faceplate (basically a ring of 200 mm and 300 mm diameters) was firmly welded to the inlet side of the drum and the cover plate including the discharge chute assembled at the other end. The entire drying chamber is axially held above the heating element by means of two pieces of P306 pillow bearings. For the purpose of facilitating proper conveyance of charged feedstock between the chutes, four (4) pieces of flights worms were intermittently fastened along the internal wall of the drying chamber (drum). More so, to prevent overheating due to stagnation of feedstock, the drying chamber was made to rotate so as to swing the feedstock as it being turned by the mechanical power transmission unit. A dimmer control switch, to which the one of the terminals of the thermostat and electric motor were connected, was incorporated as a control mechanism for presetting the drying temperature and varying the rotation speed of the electric motor. In order to prevent heat loss, the upper surface of the drying chamber was covered with a hollow-formed-semicircular box sandwiched with 50 mm thick of fibre glass (thermal insulator), to serve as the lid or top cover.

The mainframe provides support for the other components of the machine and is made of 50 mm by 50 mm by 5 mm angle iron. The parts of the machine that

could come in contact in the feedstock were made of stainless steels materials, every other (remote) parts were made of mild steel; this was done for the purpose of reducing cost of fabrication.

III RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Feedstock collection and Preparation

Specified mass of Shea nuts (feedstock) was obtained from Ilorin Metropolis, Kwara State. The feedstock was sorted to remove broken ones, sieved and cleaned to remove dirt and fragmented once.

Experimental determination of water content of the shea nuts

In order to possess the required precise data on the feedstock for evaluating the performance of the machine the initial moisture content (MC) of the procured sample was first determined. The procured feedstock was spread on mat, some samples were randomly picked and taken to the Research Laboratory of FUTA to determine their average initial moisture content (MC), represented as ϕ_1 . The moisture content was determined using oven dry method, as described by Patrick and Ojariafe, (2014)

Experimental Procedure

Prior to the commencement of the experimentation, the machine was switched on, preset to temperature of 130

°C and speed of 20 rpm with the aid of the installed dimmer control, and allowed to run for 5 minutes to ensure uniform expansion of the system.

At the commencement of the experimentation, rated mass, 10.0 kg, of the feedstock was weighed with a mass measuring scale (ATOMA A-110C), charged into the machine through its inlet chute (part labelled 1) and run for 4.0 hour.

At the end of 4.0 hour, the machine was switched off, its discharge chute (part labelled 2) opened to offload the dried feedstock. The drying time was recorded with a stopwatch, the final mass of the dried feedstock measured with the measuring scale and recorded, and the number of cracked or fragmented dried noted.

This procedure was replicated five times with equal quantity of feedstock. Figure 4 presents experimental and analysis of the evaluation.

The experimental data obtained were used to determine the drying efficiency and energy consumption of the drying machine, and assess influence of the drying operation on the drying rate, and cracking/breaking tendency of the nuts due to shrinkage caused by the moisture reduction. Table 2 presents the experimental data obtained and results of the machine performance assessment

Table 2: Experimental data and Analysis

s/n	Sample mass (kg)		Moisture (kg)	MC (%)	Moisture shrink MC_s (%) (vi)	Hourly MC reduction (%) (vii)	Time Taken (h) (viii)	Drying		Cracked nuts (pieces) (x)	Energy consumption (%) (xi)
	Before (ii)	After (iii)	Removal (iv)	Attained (v)				Rate (kg/h) (xiii)	Efficiency (%) (ix)		
1	10.01	6.07	3.93	17.82	8.26	4.46	4.0	0.9825	60.64	2	11.10
2	10.02	5.94	4.08	20.71	7.28	5.18	4.0	1.0200	59.28	9	11.53
3	10.00	6.04	3.96	18.48	6.50	4.62	4.0	0.9900	60.40	34	11.29
4	10.01	6.03	3.98	18.79	6.61	4.70	4.0	0.9950	60.24	19	11.24
5	10.00	5.99	4.01	19.47	6.84	4.87	4.0	1.0025	59.90	15	11.33
Mean	10.01		3.99		7.10	4.76	4.0	0.991	60.09		11.30

Column (vi) shows the influence of heat on the moisture contents of the charged feedstock over the entire drying period. The MC_s remained non linearly varied as the heating process progressed. However, it became high in the first-two runs, but decreased

afterward. The increased or high value of MC_s at each of the first-two experimentations could be attributed to the newness of the machine, especially the drying unit, which caused restriction of the movement of the tightly bound atoms of the heating unit (chamber)

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and made it hard for the electrons to properly transfer heat at the first-two runs, but became free and more conducting as the experimentations advanced. The high value of the moisture shrink (of 8.26 %) in the first experimentation (s/n -1) also accounted for the noticeable reduction in the corresponding drying rate (0.9825 kg/h) and energy consumption (11.10 %) of the system.

Columns (ix) and (xi) present results of the variation in the drying efficiency and energy consumption of the machine. It could be observed that the drying efficiency and energy consumption of the machine are transient, they ranged from 59.28 to 60.64 % and 11.10 to 11.53 %. The variations in them, in spite of the fact that almost same quantity of feedstock was utilized at each experimentation could be attributed to the variation in the prevailing ambient conditions (such as: temperature, humidity and air velocity) as each of the experimentation was conducted at different period of time.

The cracking rate of the shea kernel increased during the drying period as the moisture content (MC) decreased. The cracked pieces ranged from 2 to 34 pieces; the highest obtained with MC of 6.50 % and least at 8.26 % MC_s . The increase in the cracked pieces as the final MC_s attained reduced could be due to the dry bone conditions of the shells as they become friable coupled with the increase in the clearance between the shells and nuts as a result of the reduced MC. This result aligned with the findings of: Aviara *et al*, (2005) Owolarafe *et al*, (2012); Omoruyi and Ugwu (2015); Olaoye and Adekanye (2018) that kernel detaches easily from the shell, and seldom cracked, as a result of presence of sufficient clearance between them (nut and shell) due to shrinkage; Feizollah (2014) that full cracking of nut increased with decrease in MC and increased impact energy; and that shell cracks due to shrinkage of the shell as the MC decreases which caused the internal stresses to exceed the shell tensile limit

IV CONCLUSION

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A 10.0 kg per batch shea nuts (fruits) drying machine was developed and tested to assess its performance. It was developed to enhance shelf life of shea nuts and boost the productivity of its derivatives. The drying machine basically comprised the chutes (inlet and discharge), drying chamber, mechanical power transmission unit, thermal power generating unit, dimmer switch for presetting the drying temperature and varying the rotational speed of the prime mover. For the purpose of fostering proper assessment of the performance of the machine the initial moisture content of the shea fruits was determined and found as 28.04 %. The developed drying machine was used to reduce moisture content of shea fruits for four hours and its performance assessed based on the moisture removal, moisture shrink, drying rate, drying efficiency, and energy consumption. The drying rate and efficiency varied between 0.98 – 1.02 kg/h, and 59.90 – 60.64 %, whilst the energy consumption ranged between 11.10 – 11.50 %. These values implied that the use of electric drying system is an effective way for achieving controllable quick reduction in the moisture of agro-produce. The attained mean moisture reduction of 4.73 % per hour and moisture shrinkage of 7.47 % The results also revealed that shells cracked due to presence of sufficient clearance between them and their nuts as they shrink due to reduction in the moisture content. To sustain proper moisture reduction with minimum nuts cracking rate, the introduction of intermittent drying could be adopted in the future.

Thus, the use of this device would alleviate the yearning of the stakeholders, boost the production capacity of shea related products and prolong the shelf life of shea fruits

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